

THE EFFECT OF PLY ORIENTATION ON THE PEAK AND DELAMINATION THRESHOLD LOADS OF CFRP COMPOSITE PLATES

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SUMMARY: Although fibre reinforced composites can carry large in-plane loads they have poorer mechanical properties for transverse loading. A low velocity transverse impact can generate failure such as matrix cracking and/or delamination. Delamination though not visible, can significantly reduce the in-plane strength of the composite. This paper examines how the sense of a particular ply can affect the delamination threshold and maximum loads. This investigation was carried out with two families of composite plates, having the following configurations $0_3/\beta/0_3/90_3/45_3/-45_3$ and $0_3/\beta/0_{12}$, where $\beta = 0^0, 30^0, 45^0, 60^0$ and 90^0 . In both, cases the load increased with β , with the exclusion of a drop in the peak load, obtained for the $0_3/90/0_{12}$ plate, the reason being its cross ply nature.

KEYWORDS: Peak load, delamination load, impact loading, composite plates, instrumented impactor.

INTRODUCTION

Fibre composite materials are increasingly being used in a variety of structural applications. Their relatively low weight in combination with good strength and stiffness make fibre composites the preferred material in many structural applications over monolithic metals and their alloys. They are exposed to a wide spectrum of loading in service. These loads induce regions of high stress concentration in the vicinity of the contact area. The damaged characteristics of a composite material subjected to subperforation (low velocity, typically less than 5m/s) impact can be classified as indentation, fibre breakage, matrix cracking, fibre-matrix debonding and delamination. Among them delamination plays a significant role in the degradation of mechanical properties of the materials. Delaminations are as typical for composite structures as fatigue cracks are for monolithic metals and their alloys [16].

Delamination comes in a form of separation of adjoining plies. This may be caused by interlaminar stresses created by impact, eccentricities in structural load paths, discontinuities in the structure, or even during manufacturing. The presence of a delamination results in reduction in composite stiffness and strength, particularly, the compressive strength after impact. It also causes changes in parameters like buckling load, natural frequency, etc. Thus, delamination study and prevention has received considerable attention in the composite community.

In order to use composites effectively as structural components, the designer needs a sound understand of the cause of delamination and the basic for the increase in the failure resistance, which is the main focus of this paper. Delamination has a peanut-like shape and propagates along the fibre direction of the lower layer, from the direction of impact [8 & 13]. That is the longitudinal axis orients itself in the sense parallel to the direction of the fibre at of the bottom layer at the interface. The growth of delamination is very unstable [8]. The orthotropic behaviour of each ply in a laminate and the mismatch in their bending stiffness is thought to be the basic cause of delaminations [3 &15].

Tien-Wei Shyr and Yu-Hao Pan [15] reported that the random and discontinuous fibre couldn't efficiently transfer impact energy to the in-plane direction and that the structure of the reinforced material is strongly affected by the delamination pattern and area. Davies and Zhang [4] contributed that the difference between the kinetic energy of the impactor and the maximum potential energy of the structure is responsible for damage and damage is related to the energy difference.

Contact force history is an important aspect of the response of a structure to impact, and is usually used to validate a numerical scheme. Dazhi Jiang and Dongwei Shu[5] obtained the contact force history using the damage constitutive equation instead of the Hertzian contact law used by Tan and Sun[14]. The peak force and duration of the first pulse gave good agreement. The stress distribution in a laminate was analysed, without the consideration of damage and this distribution gave indication of the possible locations of delaminations. It was concluded that the stress causing the first delamination should be that which is first to reach the threshold for delamination.

Material and Sample preparation

The samples for the test were prepared from a roll of prepreg unidirectional carbon-fibre epoxy composite, having 60% fibre volume fraction, using 30⁰ and 45⁰ squares, and a blade to slice the plies to the required size. The material designated Hexply[®] 914 – TC – 5 – 34% was produced by Hexcel Composites. It has the reinforcement made of high tensile Torayco carbon having a prepreg thickness of 0.125mm. Hexply[®] is a trade mark for high performance composites and this material is used in primary aircraft structures.

The plies that make-up the laminates were stacked manually; covered with a release film and placed between aluminium plates on the bed of the autoclave (fig.1 & 2). This was covered with a bleeding material and a vacuum bag, sealed round its perimeter with a tape. A vacuum pump was connected to the valve fitted to the bagging material.

Fig. 1. Samples under vacuum pressure in the autoclave.

Fig. 2. The Autoclave

The autoclave is a pressure vessel, which provides the curing conditions for the composite where the application of vacuum pressure (fig. 3), heat up rate, and cure temperature are controlled.

Fig 3. The pressure cycle

The samples were cured in the autoclave as follows:

- ❖ A pressure of 700 kN/m² was applied.
- ❖ Heated to 175⁰C at the rate of 5⁰C per minute
- ❖ Cured for an hour at 175⁰C.

The vacuum generated was maintained throughout the curing period.

The autoclave was opened slightly, for the specimens to gradually cool to room temperature, before the vacuum pressure was released.

Impact testing

Impact tests were conducted using a *ROSAND* instrumented drop-weight impactor of energy capacity 588 J obtained by adjusting the drop height. The main features of the impact tester are as shown in fig. 4. The equipment has an unchangeable impact mass fixed at 30kg. Test were performed on laminates with the configurations 0₃/β/0₃/90₃/45₃/-45₃ and 0₃/β/0₁₂, where β = 0⁰, 30⁰, 45⁰, 60⁰ and 90⁰. The impacting mass dropped from a height of 0.015m for all test conducted. Although, there are three ways of specifying the drop position: height, energy or velocity. Obviously these parameters are related. Only one of these parameters is specified and the others are calculated from it and if necessary displayed.

The samples were rigidly clamped one after the other in the test area of the impact tester (fig. 5) and the falling weight guided onto the sample, in a defined manner. At impact, the resistive force exerted by the sample on the striker is measured as a function of time and stored for subsequent display and analysis. The system calculates the corresponding velocity history of the impactor by integrating the force history (after being divided by the mass of impactor) and with the use of initial impact velocity.

Similarly, the corresponding displacement history of the impactor was calculated from integrating the velocity history. Based on the force and displacement histories of the impactor, the energy history, which represented the history of energy transferred from the impactor to the composite, was calculated. The fracture event lasts, typically for a few thousandths of a second. Tests were repeated for two samples of each lay –up configuration. The oscillatory response was obtained. There was little variation of the peak and delamination loads.

Fig. 4. The main features of the ROSAND impact tester.

Fig. 5. The test area.

Damage inspection

Macroscopic damage modes of the composite laminate after impact include indentation, surface cracking, delamination, back face splitting and laminate splitting (see fig. 6 below). Among these delamination is an important mode of damage because the residual mechanical properties of an impacted composite laminates are strongly dependent on the delamination areas and their locations at laminate interfaces.

Fig. 6. Photographs of the composite plates after the impact test.

Experimental results and discussion

An approach for analysing the impact dynamics is to consider the balance of energy in the system. The initial kinetic energy of the impactor is used to deform the composite plate during impact. The overall deformation of the structure usually involves bending, shear deformation, and for large deformations, membrane stiffening effects. Local deformations in the contact zone also are to be considered. For impacts that induce only small amounts of damage, the energy needed to create damage may be neglected. Therefore, the energy-balance equation can be written as (1)

$$\frac{1}{2}MV^2 = E_b + E_s + E_m + E_c \quad (1)$$

Where the subscripts b , s and m refer to bending, shear and membrane components of the overall structural deformation and E_c is the energy stored in the contact region during indentation.

The threshold force of the Hertzian failure varies with different samples (see test results figs 8 – 17), an indication that each sample has its own unique load-bearing capacity. The impact damage in the bottom layer is attributed to the bending stresses as a result of impact. Fig. 7. gives an illustration of the damage phenomenon in layered composites as a result of impact [15].

Fig. 7. A typical impact damage mode for composite laminate [15].

The energy absorbing mechanism of the samples showed that fibre fracture dominated the failure model. There was also back face splitting and complete division of the laminate as in the 0_{12} and $0_3/30/0_{12}$ laminates. The magnitude of damage depended mainly on the plate configuration as the incident energy of the impactor was kept constant.

$$\text{Incident energy of impact} = m.g.h = 30 \times g \times 0.015 \quad \text{Joules}$$

Where g is the acceleration due to gravity

Internal delamination is due to the transverse shear stresses (or strain) and the threshold is associated with a sudden load drop indicating dramatic stiffness reduction and a significant damage event. Significant damage is predominantly delamination, but may include fibre breakage, local puncture or indentation.

Fig. 8. Force – displacement plot of $0_7/90_3/45_3/-45_3$ laminate

Fig. 9. Force – displacement plot of $0_3/30/0_3/90_3/45_3/-45_3$ laminate.

The peaks after the initiation of delamination represent change in mode of failure from internal delamination to plate bending, fibre breakage, back face splitting, etc. The fibre, which is the load-bearing component of the composite, fails by breakage from the maximum or peak load.

Fig. 10. Force – displacement plot of $0_3/45/0_3/90_3/45_3/-45_3$ laminate.

Fig. 11. Force – displacement plot of $0_3/60/0_3/90_3/45_3/-45_3$ laminate.

Fig. 12. Force – displacement plot of $0_3/90/0_3/90_3/45_3/-45_3$ laminate.

Fig. 13. Force – displacement plot of 0_{16} laminate.

The experimental curves contain some small oscillations during the loading. The minor peaks in the load history plot up to the peak are basically due to elastic wave responses and vibration of the specimen; while the change in direction of the slope is likely to be

associated with the introduction of intraply transverse matrix cracking or localized indentation of the specimen.

Fig. 14. Force – displacement plot of $0_3/30/0_{12}$ laminate.

Fig. 15. Force – displacement plot of $0_3/45/0_{12}$ laminate.

Among the laminates with $0_3/\beta/0_3/90_3/45_3/-45_3$ configuration, when $\beta = 0$ (fig. 8), on unloading the force does not return to its original value. There existed a partial unloading, indicative of high-energy absorption. The points of drastic load drops from the peak constitute severe failure such as fibre breakage. From the configuration of the laminates delamination is expected to initiate and propagate in $90_3/45_3$ interface and the $0_3/\beta$ interface, where $\beta = 30, 45$ & 60 .

Fig. 16. Force – displacement plot of $0_3/60/0_{12}$ laminate.

Fig. 17. Force – displacement plot of $0_3/90/0_{12}$ laminate.

The $0_3/90/0_{12}$ composite plate has a very high Hertzian failure, which is close to the peak load. This is an indication that there might be no delamination but breakage of fibre. The $0/90$ interface is crossed and there exists little interlaminar shear stress. The point on the load history where a sudden or drastic reduction in the load occurs gives the delamination threshold load or the initiation of Hertzian failure. The tables below (Tables 1 & 2) show the value of the delamination and peak loads. Near the peak a sudden load drop occurs followed by high frequency oscillations.

Table 1: Delamination and Peak loads for $0_3/\beta/0_3/90_3/45_3/-45_3$ Composite Plate

β	Delamination load (N)	Peak load (N)
0	764.9	1480
30	1266	1555
45	1530	1755
60	1718	1956
90	1894	2157

Fig. 18. Delamination load Vs β for $0_3/\beta/0_3/90_3/45_3/-45_3$ composite.

Fig. 19. Peak load Vs β for $0_3/\beta/0_3/90_3/45_3/-45_3$ composite

In the family of plies with $0_3/\beta/0_3/90_3/45_3/-45_3$ composite, as β increases the delamination and maximum load increased almost linearly. The plot can be approximated to a straight line as approximately 95% of the data points agree to the line of best fit (fig. 18 and fig. 19), i.e. the coefficient of determination (R^2).

Table 2: Delamination and Peak loads for $0_3/\beta/0_{12}$ Composite Plate

β	Delamination load (N)	Peak load (N)
0	0	978
30	790	1191
45	978	1342
60	990.6	1630
90	1241	1442

Fig. 20. Delamination load Vs β for $0_3/\beta/0_{12}$ laminate.

Fig. 21. Peak load Vs β for $0_3/\beta/0_{12}$ laminate.

The delamination load – ply orientation for the $0_3/\beta/0_{12}$ group of composites is plotted in fig. 20. The drop in peak load (fig. 21) is thought to be because the composite $0_3/90/0_{12}$ is crossed plied and the load distributed to the angles of the plate were not substantially, absorbed.

Applying the principle of linear regression. It can be generalised that delamination and maximum loads, relate approximately to the ply orientation β , as $P = m\beta + \lambda$, where m and λ are constants that relate to a family of composite configuration.

Conclusion

The design of a composite configuration requires an understanding of its resistance to delamination and fibre breakage. This paper has presented an overview of the characteristics of composites as a result of the changes in ply orientation. The approach adopted was to change the sense of a lamina in a composite through the angles 0^0 , 30^0 , 45^0 , 60^0 and 90^0 and examine the peak and delamination threshold loads from the force – displacement plot. It was noted that angle ply laminates have better resistance to failure. Hence, it is appropriate to have 30^0 , 45^0 and 60^0 in a composite structure to resist loads distributed to these directions.

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